

FLAME HANDBOOK

National Observatory of Athens

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FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

Project start date: 01.11.2020

Project end date: 31.07.2024

Budget: 163,701 €

The FLAME research project was supported by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI) under the “2nd Call for HFRI Research Projects to support Post-Doctoral Researchers” (Project Number: 00559).

H.F.R.I.
Hellenic Foundation for
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Deliverable Information

Deliverable number and name	D1.1 Project Handbook
Due date	31.12.2020
Delivery date	31.12.2020
Related work package	WP1 Project Management
Author(s)	T.M. Giannaros
Approved by	T.M. Giannaros
Dissemination level	Public
Version	0.3 (18.12.2023)

Preamble

The FLAME Project Handbook outlines the internal procedures of the research team (RT) in terms of project realization, administrative management, management structures, communication, and collaboration. It defines the rules and responsibilities of the RT members, aiming to ensure the quality and progress of the work. The goal of the FLAME Project Handbook is to ensure, coordinate and foster communication and collaboration within the RT during the entire project life.

The FLAME Project Handbook is divided into the following sections:

- Section 1 provides a brief overview of the project, including the work plan, deliverables and milestones, and the members of the RT;
- Section 2 introduces the management structure and procedures of the project, setting the roles and responsibilities of the participating researchers and relevant procedures;
- Section 3 describes the procedures that need to be followed for ensuring the quality of the project deliverables; and
- Section 4 presents information on the practices that should be followed for both internal and external communication.

The FLAME Project Handbook is a living document and can be modified according to the project needs. Throughout the lifecycle of the FLAME project, this document will be updated when necessary, extending the provided information and including relevant issues and changes in the project procedures. Each time the present document is updated, all RT members will be informed about the updates and changes made with respect to the latest version.

This document is based on the terms and conditions defined in the Grant Agreement (GA)¹. For the avoidance of doubt, the GA takes precedence over the FLAME Project Handbook.

¹ <https://osf.io/cp8hm/>

1. Introduction

1.1 General information

FLAME is a research project funded by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI), focusing on extreme fire weather and behavior. The project is carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) in Greece and is led by Associate Researcher Dr. Theodore M. Giannaros. The project's duration is 3 years (2020 – 2021) and the total approved budget equals 163,701.00€.

Table 1.1 Identity of the FLAME project.

Project title	Flammable Greece: Increasing awareness and preparedness for extreme fire weather and behavior
Project acronym	FLAME
Principal investigator	Dr. Theodore M. Giannaros (thgian@noa.gr)
Approved budget	163,701 €
Duration	01.12.2020 – 31.07.2024
Funding authority	HFRI
Host Institution	IERSD/NOA

1.2 Project objectives

The overarching goal of the FLAME project is to advance the scientific knowledge of extreme fire weather and behavior in order to increase awareness and preparedness in Greece. Upon this goal, the following specific objectives are identified:

- To compile the climatology of critical fire weather patterns, determining their frequency, duration and strength during a typical fire season in Greece, and investigating any relationships between their occurrence and atmospheric teleconnections (e.g., NAO, AO, ENSO) or/and sea-surface temperature (SST) anomalies.
- To study the processes and conditions under which major transitions in fire behavior take place, determining potential threshold conditions that could be used for predicting extreme fire behavior.

To advance fire behavior modeling, in particular with respect to accurate spread prediction, by incorporating the concept of atmospheric stability in a coupled fire-atmosphere modeling system.

1.3 Work plan

The FLAME project is articulated in 6 work packages (WPs), broken down in 17 tasks:

- **WP1: Project Management**
The objective of this WP is to manage, monitor, and coordinate the scientific and financial realization of the project. The specific tasks included in this WP are:
Task 1.1: FLAME Handbook
Task 1.2: Project Management
Task 1.3: Periodic Management Reports

- **WP2: Critical Fire Weather Patterns**
The objective of this WP is to derive the critical fire weather patterns of Greece, determining their key characteristics and investigating any possible relationships with atmospheric teleconnections and/or SST anomalies. The specific tasks included in this WP are:
Task 2.1: Data Collection
Task 2.2: SOM
Task 2.3: VPD
Task 2.4: Critical Fire Weather Patterns

- **WP3: Synoptic and Sub-synoptic Dynamics**
The objective of this WP is to describe and characterize the dynamical processes of Greece's critical fire weather patterns, verifying the definition of threshold conditions that could be used for predicting extreme fire behavior. The specific tasks included in this WP are:
Task 3.1: Extreme Wildfires Database
Task 3.2: Numerical Simulations
Task 3.3: Dynamics Study

- **WP4: Fire Spread Modeling**
The objective of this WP is to explicitly account for the concept of atmospheric stability in a coupled fire-atmosphere modeling system by developing and testing a wind gust parameterization. The specific tasks included in this WP are:
Task 4.1: Gust Parameterization Development
Task 4.2: Gust Parameterization Evaluation
Task 4.2: Numerical Experiments

- **WP5: Dissemination**

The objective of this WP is to promote the publicity of the project, raising awareness about its outcomes and achievements. The specific tasks included in this WP are:

Task 5.1: Dissemination Plan

Task 5.2: FLAME Webpage

Task 5.3: Outreach Material

Task 5.4: Publications and Conferences

Detailed information about the work that will be conducted in each WP and each task can be found in the Grant Agreement (GA) document.

1.4 Deliverables and milestones

The FLAME project includes 25 deliverables and 15 milestones, summarized in Tables 1.2 and 1.3, respectively. Due dates reflect amendments applied to the original GA.

Table 1.2 List of FLAME deliverables ordered by due date.

ID	Name	WP	Task	Dissemination level ²	Due date
Year 1 (01/12/2020 – 30/11/2021)					
D1.1	Project Handbook	1	1.1	PU	31/12/2020
D5.1	Dissemination Plan	5	5.1	CO	28/02/2021
D5.2	Webpage	5	5.2	PU	31/05/2021
D5.3	e-Newsletter vol. 1	5	5.3	PU	31/05/2021
D1.2	1 st Periodic Progress Report	1	1.3	CO	30/11/2021
D5.3	e-Newsletter vol. 2	5	5.3	PU	30/11/2021
Year 2 (01/12/2021 – 30/11/2022)					
D2.1	Critical Fire Weather Patterns Handbook	2	2.4	PU	30/11/2022

² PU: Public, CO: Confidential

D2.2	Critical Fire Weather Patterns Database	2	2.4	PU	30/11/2022
D3.1	Extreme Wildfires Database	3	3.1	PU	31/05/2022
D5.3	e-Newsletter vol. 3	5	5.3	PU	31/05/2022
D1.3	2 nd Periodic Progress Report	1	1.3	CO	30/11/2022
D5.3	e-Newsletter vol. 4	5	5.3	PU	30/11/2022
D5.4	Promotional Video 1	5	5.3	PU	30/11/2021

Year 3 (01/12/2022 – 31/07/2024)

D3.2	Extreme Fire Weather Simulations	3	3.2	CO	30/04/2023
D3.3	Dynamics Discussion	3	3.3	PU	31/10/2023
D4.1	WRF-SFIRE Wind Gust Parameterization	4	4.1	PU	30/11/2023
D4.2	Wind Gust Parameterization Evaluation Report	4	4.2	PU	30/11/2023
D5.3	e-Newsletter vol. 5	5	5.3	PU	31/05/2023
D1.4	3 rd Periodic Progress Report	1	1.3	CO	31/07/2024
D1.5	Final Project Report	1	1.3	PU	31/07/2024
D4.3	Atmospheric Instability Assessment Report	4	4.3	PU	31/07/2024
D5.3	e-Newsletter vol. 6	5	5.3	PU	30/11/2023
D5.4	Promotional Video 2	5	5.3	PU	30/11/2023
D5.5	Policy Brief	5	5.3	PU	31/07/2024
D5.6	List of Publications	5	5.4	PU	31/07/2024

Table 1.3 List of FLAME milestones ordered by due date.

ID	Name	WP	Task	Due date
Year 1 (01/12/2020 – 30/11/2021)				
M5.1	Webpage	5	5.2	31/05/2021
M2.1	SOM-based Weather Types	2	2.2	30/06/2021
M2.2	Critical VPD Thresholds	2	2.3	30/06/2021
M1.2	Periodic Progress Reporting 1	1	1.3	30/11/2021
Year 2 (01/12/2021 – 30/11/2022)				
M1.1	Finalization of Staff Contracts	1	1.2	31/05/2022
M2.3	Critical Fire Weather Patterns	2	2.3	31/05/2022
M3.1	Extreme Wildfires Database	3	3.1	31/05/2022
M1.3	Periodic Progress Reporting 2	1	1.3	30/11/2022
Year 3 (01/12/2022 – 30/11/2023)				
M3.2	Extreme Fire Weather Simulations	3	3.2	31/01/2023
M4.1	Gust Parameterization Development	4	4.1	31/01/2023
M4.2	Gust Parameterization Evaluation	4	4.2	30/04/2023
M1.4	Periodic Progress Reporting 3	1	1.3	30/11/2023
M4.3	Atmospheric Instability Assessment	4	4.3	30/11/2023
M5.2	Policy Brief	5	5.3	30/11/2023
M5.3	List of Publications	5	5.4	30/11/2023

1.5 Research team

The FLAME RT comprises 7 members: 2 Researchers, 1 Research Scientist, 3 Post-doctoral Researchers, and 1 Technical Assistant.

Table 1.4 List of FLAME RT members with contact details.

Name	Employment	Email
Dr. Theodore M. Giannaros	Associate Researcher	thgian@noa.gr
Dr. Vassiliki Kotroni	Research Director	kotroni@noa.gr
Dr. Katerina Papapagiannaki	Research Scientist B	katpap@noa.gr
Dr. Sakis Karagiannidis	Post-doctoral Researcher	thankar@live.com
Dr. Elisavet Galanaki	Post-doctoral Researcher	galanakia@noa.gr
Dr. Georgios Papavassileiou	Post-doctoral Researcher	papavasileiou@noa.gr
M.Sc. Antonis Bezes	Technical Assistant	antonisbezés@gmail.com

2. Project management structure and procedures

The management structure of the FLAME project is illustrated in Fig. 2.1 It encompasses 3 layers of decision-making in order to safeguard the effective cooperation between the RT members and to guarantee the production of high-quality deliverables throughout the project duration.

Figure 2.1 Management structure of the FLAME project.

2.1 Principal investigator

Dr. Theodore M. Giannaros is the Principal Investigator (PI) and coordinator of the FLAME project. The PI will be responsible for the oversight and coordination of the entire project, acting as the intermediary between the RT, the Funding Authority (FA) and the Management Unit of Special Research Account (MUSRA) of NOA. He will also be responsible for carrying out the tasks assigned to him, as specified in the GA and in this document.

The PI will be the single point of contact with the FA and in charge of the overall administrative management of the FLAME project. In that regard, he will be responsible for carrying out the financial and scientific management of the project, ensuring effective communication and collaboration within the RT by defining all necessary procedures. In particular, the PI will:

- arrange and chair meetings of the RT members;
- monitor the conducted work in close collaboration with the Work Package Leaders (WPLs);
- collect, review and submit reports and other deliverable items, or any other requested document, to the FA; and
- fulfill promptly and on time all financial tasks.

Overall, the PI should ensure that all procedures followed during the entire project life are compatible with the guidelines of the FA, as documented in the Project Management Guide (PMG).

2.2 Work package leader

Each WP of the FLAME project will be led by one WPL, assisted by one co-leader. WPLs will be responsible for the day-to-day management within their WPs. In particular, the responsibilities of the WPL include:

- leading and coordinating the activities involved in each WP through the Task Leaders (TLs),
- carrying out initial quality control checks on the deliverables,
- highlighting to the PI potential risks and deviations from the agreed work plan; and
- reporting (internally) progress to the PI.

Table 2.1 presents the WPLs and co-leaders assigned for the execution of the FLAME project.

Table 2.1. WPLs and co-leaders of the FLAME project.

WP	WPL	Co-leader
WP1: Project Management	Theodore M. Giannaros	Vassiliki Kotroni
WP2: Critical Fire Weather Patterns	Georgios Papavassileiou	Katerina Papagiannaki
WP3: Synoptic and Sub-synoptic Dynamics	Vassiliki Kotroni	Georgios Papavassileiou
WP4: Fire Spread Modeling	Theodore M. Giannaros	Georgios Papavassileiou
WP5: Dissemination	Katerina Papagiannaki	Elisavet Galanaki

2.3 Task leader

Tasks defined in each WP of the FLAME project are not to be considered as simple sub-divisions of the work, but rather as key elements of the project with a significant amount of autonomy, jointly contributing to the objectives of the WP. In that regard, TLs and co-leaders have been also assigned (Table 2.2) in order to maintain a solid structure characterized by individual partners responsible for individual actions. TLs will be in charge of the work carried out in the respective tasks, coordinating relevant activities and making day-to-day technical decisions. They will also be responsible for the timely production of the associated deliverables. TLs should report progress (internally) to the WPL every month (minimum obligation).

Table 2.2. Tls and co-leaders of the FLAME project

Task	TL	Co-leader
T1.1: FLAME Handbook	Theodore M. Giannaros	Vassiliki Kotroni
T1.2: Project Administration	Theodore M. Giannaros	Vassiliki Kotroni
T1.3: Periodic Management Reports	Theodore M. Giannaros	Vassiliki Kotroni
T2.1: Data Collection	Theodore M. Giannaros	Katerina Papagiannaki
T2.2: SOM	Georgios Papavassileiou	Theodore M. Giannaros
T2.3: VPD	Katerina Papagiannaki	Theodore M. Giannaros
T2.4: Critical Fire Weather Patterns	Georgios Papavassileiou	Theodore M. Giannaros
T3.1: Extreme Wildfires Database	Elisavet Galanaki	Katerina Papagiannaki
T3.2: Numerical Simulations	Theodore M. Giannaros	Vassiliki Kotroni
T3.3: Dynamics Study	Georgios Papavassileiou	Vassiliki Kotroni
T4.1:	Theodore M. Giannaros	Vassiliki Kotroni

Gust Development	Parameterization		
T4.2:		Georgios Papavassileiou	Theodore M. Giannaros
Gust Evaluation	Parameterization		
T4.3:		Georgios Papavassileiou	Theodore M. Giannaros
Numerical Experiments			
T5.1:		Theodore M. Giannaros	Katerina Papagiannaki
Dissemination Plan			
T5.2:		Antonis Bezes	Theodore M. Giannaros
FLAME Webpage			
T5.3:		Elisavet Galanaki	Sakis Karagiannidis
Outreach Material			
T5.4:		Theodore M. Giannaros	Sakis Karagiannidis
Publications and Conferences			

2.4 Meetings

Several meetings will be held throughout the life of the FLAME project in order to ensure the efficient monitoring of project activities and promote collaboration among the members of the RT. In particular, the following meetings are foreseen:

- **Bi-monthly progress meetings**

Progress meetings will take place every other month, in order to discuss the progress of the ongoing tasks and work plan. During busy periods, progress meetings may be held once every month. The PI will be responsible for arranging and holding these meetings, informing the RT members that need to participate at least 10 days prior to the meeting date.

- **Annual project meetings**

Once a year, a plenary meeting will be held. All RT members will participate to this meeting, whose purpose will be to monitor the overall progress of the project (work that has been

conducted and future planning) and enhance cooperation among the RT members. The first annual meeting will be held between January 2021, while the second and third annual meetings are foreseen to be held between February – April 2022 and February – April 2023, respectively.

All meetings will be held either face-to-face, subject to restrictions related to the SARS-Cov-2 pandemic, or by teleconference (e.g., Zoom). For each meeting, the PI will be responsible for keeping meeting minutes, which he should make available to all RT members.

2.5 Reporting

Over the course of the FLAME project, reporting will be carried out on the following levels:

- **Monthly progress reports (MPRs)**

MPRs will be submitted to the PI no later than 5 days prior to the end of the reporting period. These reports will summarize the work conducted over the reporting period, and they must be compiled by the following RT members: (i) Research Associate, (ii) Sakis Karagiannidis, (iii) Elisavet Galanaki, and (iv) Antonis Bezes. Besides being an effective tool for monitoring the work progress, it should be underlined that MPRs are obligatory for the execution of payments for the above-mentioned RT members.

- **Periodic management reports (PMRs)**

According to the GA and the PMG, the FLAME project is divided into 3 reporting periods: (i) from 01/12/2020 (month 1) to 30/11/2021 (month 12), (ii) from 01/12/2021 (month 13) to 30/11/2022 (month 24), and (iii) from 01/12/2022 (month 25) to 30/11/2023 (month 36). At the end of each reporting period, and no later than 75 days after its end, the PI will be responsible for submitting PMRs to the FA. These reports will be compiled by the PI based on input from all RT members and will include: (i) information on the work progress, including dissemination actions, (ii) the list of accomplished deliverables and achieved milestones, (iii) information on the financial realization of the project, (iv) copies of all legal documents related to project expenses, and (v) a detailed description and justification of changes made in the scientific and/or financial execution of the project.

- **Final project report (FPR)**

Following the completion of the FLAME project, the PI will submit the FPR to the FA, no later than 30 days following the project's end date. The FPR will be compiled based on input from all RT members, and it will include: (i) information on the work conducted throughout the project life, including dissemination actions, (ii) the list of all accomplished deliverables and achieved milestones, (iii) a detailed presentation of the financial execution of the project,

including all legal documents that support the expenses' eligibility, (iv) an extended synopsis of the FPR itself (in Greek and English), and (v) a detailed description and justification of changes made in the scientific and/or financial execution of the project.

To ensure the timely submission of the PMRs and the FPR, all RT members are requested to respect the deadlines reported in the Table 2.3. Microsoft Word templates for all types of reports will be prepared by the PI and be made available to all RT members for downloading.

Table 2.3 Reporting calendar of the FLAME project.

Report	Reporting period	Template made available	Deadline for submission of input by RT members	Due date
1 st PMR	01/12/2020 – 30/11/2021	31.10.2021	10.01.2022	31.01.2022
2 nd PMR	01/12/2021 – 30/11/2022	31.10.2022	10.01.2023	31.01.2023
3 rd PMR	01/12/2022 – 30/11/2023	31.10.2023	10.01.2024	31.01.2024
FPR	01/12/2021 – 30/11/2023	31.10.2023	10.01.2024	31.01.2024

2.6 Risks and contingency plans

The roadmap of the FLAME project could be negatively affected by a number of risks. To reduce the probability of these events, a set of structural measures (contingency plans) has been conceived.

Table 2.4 Risks and contingency plans of the FLAME project.

Description of risk	Probability	WP	Mitigation measures
Unsuccessful implementation of the synoptic classification approach	Low	2	Alternative approaches will be examined and applied

Inability to derive conceptual models	Low	3	Existing conceptual models will be properly adapted
Lack of computation resources	Low	3, 4	Numerical simulations will be carried out on the high-performance computing (HPC) infrastructure of the Greek Research and Technology Network

3. Deliverable management and procedures

WPLs and associated co-leaders (Table 2.1) will be responsible for coordinating and monitoring the production of their deliverables. TLs and associated co-leaders (Table 2.2) will act as deliverable authors (DAs), being in charge of the timely accomplishment of their deliverables.

3.1 Quality assurance procedures

All deliverables will be internally reviewed by the RT prior to their submission to the FA. The reviewing procedure will evaluate the consistency of the deliverable content in terms of its scientific soundness, completeness, and agreement with the objectives and summary defined in the GA.

The quality review procedure that will be implemented within the life of the FLAME project is summarized in Table 3.1. All RT members are requested to respect the deadlines in order to ensure the smooth execution of the work plan and the timely delivery of all deliverables. Briefly, DAs will be responsible for sending, 4 weeks prior to the due date, the first draft version of the deliverables to the associated WPLs and the PI. The WPLs and the PI will provide their comments within 2 weeks' time, and the DA will have 1 additional week to revise the deliverable accordingly. Finally, WPLs and the PI will review the revised deliverable, and the PI will be responsible for its submission to the FA, no later than the last working day of the due month.

Table 3.1 Timetable of quality review procedure for the deliverables of the FLAME project.

Date	Action
Day 1 of the month the deliverable is due	The DA sends the first draft version of the deliverable to the associated WPL and the PI
Over the next 2 weeks, the WPL and the PI review the deliverable and provide, if necessary, comments to the responsible DA. Track changes must be used.	
Day 14 of the month the deliverable is due	The WPL and the PI send the deliverable back to the DA with annotated comments
Over the next 1 week, the DA revises the deliverable according to the comments submitted by the WPL and the PI. Track changes must be used.	
Day 21 of the month of the deliverable is due	The DA sends the revised draft version of the deliverable to the associated WPL and the PI
Over the next 1 week, the WPL and the PI carry out the final check of the deliverable	
Last working day of the month the deliverable is due	The PI submits the deliverable to the FA

3.2 Storage and access

The Zenodo platform will be primarily used for file storage. The FLAME community platform has been already set up on Zenodo and can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/communities/flame>. The Zenoo FLAME community will be used for sharing working documents, exchanging important information, and uploading project deliverables.

The FLAME project will follow an open access strategy. All information related to the scientific realization of the project will be publicly and freely available to anyone through the project platform, subject to a CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International License. Deliverables and other information that have been classified as confidential in the GA (see also Table 1.2), as well as sensitive personal data, will be privately stored and accessed only by RT members.

4. Communication and dissemination

4.1 Internal communication

Internal communication is considered to be the communication taking place between members of the RT. This day-to-day communication will be carried out by email, phone calls, and teleconference means (e.g., Zoom).

With respect to the use of emails, all RT members are advised to adopt a specific convention for the Subject header, in order to facilitate communication by quickly recognizing FLAME project related emails. In particular, when exchanging emails related to the FLAME project, the following general rule must be applied for the Subject header:

[Subject: FLAME: *WP*<*x*> (if applicable) – *Issue* – *Deadline* (if applicable)]

Example:

Subject: FLAME: WP1 – Project Handbook review – 28 December 2020

For important issues, senders must include the PI in carbon copy (cc). Contact information can be found in Table 1.4.

4.2 Funding acknowledgement

All FLAME outreach material, including scientific publications and conference presentations, must include the following acknowledgment text, and if possible, the logo of the FA:

The research project was supported by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I.) under the “2nd Call for H.F.R.I. Research Projects to support Post-Doctoral Researchers” (Project Number: 00559)

4.3 Project logo

The official logo of the FLAME project must be included in all presentations and communication materials.

4.4 Presentations

All presentations related to the FLAME project should be preferably prepared in Microsoft PowerPoint format.

4.5 Social media

The PI will be responsible for establishing the following official social media accounts for the FLAME project:

- Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/flame.research.project>)
- Twitter feed (https://twitter.com/FLAME_NOA)

In all social media channels, RT members are encouraged to make use of the following hashtags:
#FLAME #meteogr #nationalobservatoryofathens #elidek

PROJECT HANDBOOK

Dr. T.M. **Giannaros**, Fire Meteorologist, Associate Researcher, IERSD/NOA

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